

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

SCIENCE PRODUCERS

As Stewards of Trust (SOT), **Science Producers** focus on conducting research, producing new knowledge, and developing scientific innovations.

**Science
Producers**

Examples: Science producers encompass a wide range of actors (individual and institutional), including scientists, research institutions, government agencies, private sector innovators, and members of public-private partnerships (PPPs) in science, technology, and innovation (STI).

Why trust in science matters for Science Producers

Despite the growing visibility of scientific research via digital and social media, the internal processes of knowledge production often remain opaque, limiting transparency, public understanding, and meaningful engagement. Research systems continue to be shaped by hyper-competitive funding environments, disciplinary silos, and performance metrics that prioritise output over collaboration or societal relevance (von Schomberg, 2024). This output-driven culture can discourage open science, interdisciplinary approaches, and co-creation with the public, weakening the perception of science as a public good (Gurzawska et al., 2024).

At the same time, research environments are undergoing profound changes, including the rise of new forms of research collaboration and funding mechanisms, cross-sector partnerships, and the increasing integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in scientific workflows. These shifts offer opportunities to accelerate knowledge production and broaden participation, but also raise questions around transparency, fairness, and accountability. Closely related is the growing politicisation and privatisation of science, which risks undermining scientific freedom, distorting research agendas, and eroding public confidence in the neutrality and integrity of science. If not addressed with care, these changes may deepen existing concerns about elitism, bias, and loss of epistemic authority.

Systemic delays caused by bureaucratic procedures, internal review cycles, and misalignments between research and policy timelines further limit science's ability to respond to grand challenges and urgent societal needs. Administrative burdens reduce researchers' capacity to conduct high-quality, socially responsive inquiry. In fragile contexts like conflict zones or among vulnerable groups, issues of transparency, openness, and community feedback are amplified. Low awareness of open research infrastructures further limits trust and inclusivity.

How can Science Producers foster trust in science?

To foster trust, science producers must actively **commit to transparent, ethical, and participatory practices**. This includes ensuring rigorous and reproducible methods, disclosing funding and potential conflicts of interest, and adopting inclusive open science frameworks. Strengthening communication, rethinking incentive structures, and embedding co-creation into research design are all critical to affirming **science as a public good**. In increasingly complex and dynamic research environments, trust must be built through

ongoing, reciprocal relationships, not only with the public, but across the broader ecosystem of trust.

Building Trustworthy Science

Scientific Quality, Accountability, and Sustainability

- Ensure rigorous methods, reproducibility, and methodological transparency, including in the use of AI in science.
- Promote adherence to standardised protocols and peer review to enhance the credibility and comparability of research findings.
- Mandate transparent disclosure of funding sources and potential conflicts of interest to reduce bias and foster credibility.
- Establish robust research management systems that delegate administrative and financial tasks to avoid overloading scientists.

Scientific Transparency, Accessibility, and Open Science

- Develop open science guidelines that are field-specific, inclusive, clear, relevant, and accessible to the general public and marginalised groups (including those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults).
- Promote openness in data, publications, and research practices, including the use of AI, to build transparency and enhance credibility.

Research Integrity and Ethics

- Ensure independent research validation, robust quality assurance, and ethical oversight for both publicly and privately funded research and enforce consequences for violations to uphold standards.

Public Engagement, Inclusivity and Benefit Sharing

- Redesign academic career structures, curricula, and incentives to value societal contributions and incentivise public trust-building efforts.
- Demonstrate and communicate real-world benefits of science in everyday life.
- Raise awareness about the importance of both basic and applied science in meeting societal goals and addressing societal challenges.
- Engage communities throughout research processes to respect local knowledge, embrace diverse perspectives, and embed values such as fairness, respect, care, and honesty into practices to address societal needs.
- Foster co-creative approaches and address power dynamics to strengthen inclusive collaboration among all stakeholders, including scientists and citizens within the ecosystem of trust in science.

Engaging the Public in Scientific Processes

Building Frameworks for Sustainable Engagement

- Shift from one-way deficit models of science communication towards relational approaches that foster mutual trust through dialogue and meaningful engagement.
- Break silos between mainstream research and citizen engagement by integrating the public as active contributors to research processes.

Recognising, Funding, and Rewarding Public Engagement

- Reward scientists and stakeholders for public engagement through dedicated funding schemes and inclusion in academic evaluation metrics. Promote openness in data, publications, and research practices, including the use of AI, to build transparency and enhance credibility.
- Establish fair compensation mechanisms for citizen contributions and recognise public engagement as integral to research impact.
- Advocate for inclusive authorship policies in academic publishing to credit citizen contributions.

Tailored Approaches

- Make scientific processes more inclusive by actively involving marginalised and underrepresented groups (particularly those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults), using approaches tailored to socio-demographic factors, belief profiles, and community-specific needs.
- Identify the diverse characteristics and needs of different communities through consultative social scientific methods such as interviews and focus groups, which will provide insights for designing and implementing tailored strategies for public engagement.

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

- Create communities of practice that bring together researchers and citizens to share knowledge, co-develop quality standards, and identify best practices for public engagement, supported by clear guidelines, practical training, and realistic planning tools.
- Encourage scientists to incorporate local knowledge and address community-specific needs.
- Cultivate public interest in science through hands-on activities, interactive tools, and citizen co-creation projects.

Fostering Critical Thinking

- Combat mis/disinformation by actively engaging with the public, collaborating with civil society, and disseminating research results.

Monitoring and Sustainability

- Implement clear and consistent feedback mechanisms to ensure participants remain informed and engaged throughout and beyond the research process.
- Adapt feedback mechanisms to specific challenges of research in fragile contexts (e.g. high-risk regions or socio-economically vulnerable settings).

Educating and Raising Awareness

Public Education on Science Fundamentals

- Promote public understanding of the scientific method, including uncertainty, falsifiability, and the iterative process, to counter misconceptions and mistrust.
- Make complex scientific concepts accessible to the public without compromising accuracy.
- Promote public awareness of the economic and social benefits of science, while fostering critical thinking, informed questioning of science-based interventions, and support for responsible research and innovation.
- Offer regular refresher courses for teachers at all educational levels to keep them up to date with current scientific research and responsible research practices to support them in raising informed future citizens.

Targeted and Inclusive Outreach

- Provide educators and science communicators with tools to address misconceptions and effectively communicate the societal benefits of science.

Bridging Academia, Industry, and Public

- Encourage collaborative projects between academia, industry and civil society to enhance practical education and innovation.
- Clarify how scientists contribute to research, policymaking, and implementation, to show how science supports society.

Science Communication

Systemic Reform, Incentives and Infrastructure Development

- Reform academic and institutional systems to value science communication and societal impact alongside traditional metrics (e.g., peer-reviewed publications), and ensure researchers have access to dedicated funding, resources, and training to support these activities.
- Introduce dedicated and professionally trained intermediaries within research institutions to support engagement with the public, media, policymakers, and industry, thereby reducing the outreach burden on individual scientists.

Transparency and Accessibility

- Make all scientific findings, including non-confirmatory results, widely accessible through open access, multilingual resources, and jargon-free communication.
- Enhance public understanding of basic science by communicating its long-term potential and the value of foundational discoveries, even in the absence of immediate practical outcomes.

Tailored and Effective Communication Strategies

- Tailor science communication strategies to specific audiences based on demographics, culture, and trust levels, and use engaging formats such as storytelling, videos, infographics, and relatable success stories to improve accessibility.
- Leverage social media and digital platforms (e.g., Instagram Live, podcasts) to reach different audiences. Collaborate with reliable science influencers and support the development of strong digital identities for science communicators to enhance credibility.

Media Collaboration, Training and Community Engagement

- Strengthen collaboration between scientists and journalists by fostering mutual trust and offering joint training opportunities.
- Encourage scientific communicators to participate in public outreach events (e.g., European Researchers' Night) to strengthen public engagement.
- Promote meaningful, two-way communication between scientists, civil society, local stakeholders, and the public, focusing on local needs, building trust, and using clear, respectful language that highlights the benefits of science.

Crisis Communication, Neutrality and Ethics

- Develop and regularly update emergency science communication plans that emphasise transparency, highlight scientific consensus, and openly address

uncertainties and conflicting findings in real-time to maintain public trust and counter mis/disinformation.

- Promote science communication that is transparent, evidence-based, and accountable, which is free from partisan or corporate bias, clear about uncertainties, and open about values, limitations, and funding sources.
- Avoid overselling scientific findings and instead provide balanced narratives that reflect both advantages and limitations of the research.

Combatting Mis/Disinformation

- Promote science and media literacy across society to enable critical assessment of information and engage with evidence-informed knowledge.

Building Supportive Policy Frameworks

Align Science with Public Interests while Safeguarding Scientific Freedom

- Align research priorities with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to address global Grand Challenges and ensure equitable benefit-sharing from scientific advancements.

Strengthen Public Research and its Autonomy

- Strengthen research governance by establishing and regularly revising quality assurance procedures, monitoring research compliance with established rules, mitigating societal risks and supporting institutional reputation through transparent and consistent practices.

Bridge Science and Industry

- Encourage the use of high-quality scientific evidence to address industry challenges (e.g., recycling, litter reduction), and facilitate its application through iterative testing and cross-sector collaboration.

Ensure Political and Public Engagement

- Foster inclusive collaboration and mutual understanding between scientists, policymakers, and the public. Balance power dynamics among stakeholders and promote consensus-building approaches.

Collaboration

Institutionalise and Strengthen Cross-Sector Collaboration

- Foster interdisciplinary, international, and cross-sector collaboration by creating multi-level platforms for knowledge exchange, best practice sharing, and policy development that actively involve policymakers, industry, educators, and civil society.
- Strengthen coordination both within and between policy makers, funders, scientific actors, and other relevant organisations, across departments, levels, and sectors, to overcome institutional silos and enable coherent policy implementation.
- Engage citizens in co-designing and evaluating research by addressing participation barriers, especially for marginalised groups such as those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults, and fostering inclusion through collaboration with local networks and community initiatives.

Enhance Collaboration through Mutual Understanding and Translation

- Build science-for-policy mechanisms that connect research with policy needs, ensuring timely and actionable outputs while safeguarding scientific freedom.
- Encourage partnerships between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create science and align research with societal needs, ensuring transparency, accountability, and shared benefits.

Foster Ethical and Open Research Practices

- Strengthen the culture of research ethics and integrity through inclusive collaboration between academic and non-academic stakeholders.

Leverage Influential Stakeholders

- Strengthen ties between all Stewards of Trust and local communities and build effective connections across diverse stakeholder groups.

Adopt Sustainable Collaboration

- Foster collaboration among Stewards of Trust by creating incentives and mutual benefits that encourage long-term partnerships.

Science Producers in the ecosystem of trust in science

Science producers are situated within a complex, interdependent ecosystem involving policy, education, communication, and civil society, as well as oversight, funding, and implementation

actors. These relationships are not merely functional but strategic, aiming to ensure that scientific knowledge is accessible, ethically grounded, socially responsive, and actionable.

By engaging with policymakers, educators, communicators, and civil society, science producers help shape evidence-informed decisions, foster public understanding, and co-create research agendas that reflect societal needs. At the same time, oversight mechanisms and funding structures are shaped by and responsive to scientific developments, reinforcing accountability and sustainability. These inter-SOT interactions are essential not only for maximising public trust in science but also for addressing the above persistent challenges that science producers face in building and maintaining public trust. In an era of mis/disinformation, distributed trust and contested expertise, such integrated relationships are critical for demonstrating the relevance, transparency, and legitimacy of scientific work.

References

Gurzawska, A., Drummond, O., Zamorano Barrios, M. M., & Yalaz, E. (2024). D4.1 Verity Synthesis Report: Mapping the new Ecosystem of Trust in science in a changing research environment. Zenodo.

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